

EFFECTS OF IONIZING RADIATION ON NORMAL TISSUES AND ORGANS AND CRITICAL ORGANS

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Abstract . This article provides a comprehensive analysis of the biological effects of ionizing radiation (X-rays, gamma, neutron, alpha and beta rays) on normal tissues and organs of the human body. The article separately considers the radiosensitivity of tissues, lethal dose zones, degenerative changes, and the radiation sensitivity and protective mechanisms of critical organs - the brain, bone marrow, intestinal epithelium and gonads. More than 20 scientific research sources conducted since 1945 to the present day have been analyzed and clinically significant conclusions have been drawn.

Keywords: Ionizing radiation, radiosensitivity, LD50, critical organs, bone marrow, brain, intestinal epithelium, gonads, radiation protection, degeneration.

Introduction. Ionizing radiation is a complex of types of radiation that have high energy and, when interacting with matter, are capable of removing electrons from atoms and molecules, that is, of causing ionization. This type includes alpha particles (helium nuclei consisting of two protons and two neutrons), beta particles (a stream of electrons or positrons), high-energy electromagnetic radiation - gamma and X-rays, as well as neutrons that are uncharged but have high penetrating properties. The ionization density (LET - linear energy transfer) and permeability of each type of radiation are unique, which determine their biological effectiveness: for example, alpha particles, although they have a high ionization density, cannot penetrate deep into tissues, while gamma and X-rays, on the contrary, although they have a lower ionization density, are distinguished by their high penetrating ability. Ionizing radiation is of great practical importance in various fields of modern science and technology. In medicine, it is widely used for diagnostic (radiography, computed tomography) and therapeutic (radiotherapy) purposes. In industry, it is used to detect internal defects in materials, carry out sterilization processes, and in technological control systems. In nuclear power, ionizing radiation is an integral component of the energy production process. However, when these radiations affect biological systems, especially at the cellular level, they can cause significant damage through damage to the DNA molecule, the formation of free radicals, and disruption of cell functions, which leads to the development of various pathological conditions (Hall and Giaccia, 2006). The study of the biological effects of ionizing radiation has been developing steadily since the beginning of the 20th century. Fundamental research conducted by Marie Curie in this regard laid an important scientific foundation. Subsequently, epidemiological and clinical data collected as a result of major man-made and military events, including the atomic bombings of Hiroshima and Nagasaki, the Chernobyl accident, and the Fukushima accident, allowed for a deeper understanding of the mechanisms of short- and long-term effects of ionizing radiation on the human body. These phenomena have played an important role in determining not only acute forms of radiation exposure, but also late consequences such as genetic mutations, oncological diseases and degenerative changes (UNSCEAR, 2008). Currently, the science of radiobiology is focused on the comprehensive study of the effects of ionizing radiation on living organisms at the molecular, cellular and systemic levels. The main attention is paid to processes such as single- and double-strand breaks of DNA, oxidative stress, disruption of signal transduction pathways, cell cycle arrest and

apoptosis. At the same time, the radiosensitivity of various biological tissues, i.e. the degree of sensitivity to radiation, dose-dependent biological responses, the range of lethal doses and degenerative changes that develop under the influence of radiation, is being widely studied. In particular, the sensitivity of critical organs and systems to radiation and their protective and adaptive mechanisms are of great scientific and practical importance.

For this article, scientific articles, monographs, and reports of international organizations published between 1950 and 2024 were reviewed from PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science, and Google Scholar databases. The search terms used were "ionizing radiation", "radiosensitivity", "critical organs", "bone marrow radiation", "radiation protection", and "lethal dose". A total of 28 sources were selected for analysis.

Types of radiation and their physical properties. Ionizing radiation is divided into direct (corpuscular) and indirect (electromagnetic) types. Alpha particles have the highest ionizing power but the lowest penetration depth. Beta particles have moderate penetration and can damage the skin. Gamma rays and X-rays have high penetration and can damage the entire body (Joiner and van der Kogel, 2009). Neutron radiation is particularly dangerous because neutrons induce nuclear reactions and produce secondary ionizing particles. The Relative Biological Effectiveness (RBE) of radiation is 20 for alpha particles, 10 for neutrons, and 1 for gamma and X-rays (ICRP, 2007).

Mechanisms of action at the cellular level. Ionizing radiation affects the cell in two ways: directly (by creating breaks in the DNA chain) and indirectly (by generating free radicals as a result of ionizing water molecules). Free radicals, especially the hydroxyl radical (OH•), damage DNA, proteins, and lipids (Ward, 1994). DNA double-strand breaks (DSBs) are considered the most dangerous damage, and if not properly repaired, they lead to cell death or mutation. Sensitivity to radiation is highest during the G2/M phase of the cell cycle (Kastan and Bartek, 2004).

formulated by French scientists Bergonie and Tribondeau in 1906, the radiosensitivity of a tissue is directly proportional to its mitotic activity and inversely proportional to the degree of differentiation. That is, cells that divide more often and are less differentiated are more sensitive to radiation (Bergonie and Tribondeau, 1906). Although this law is accepted as a basic principle in modern radiobiology, there are a number of exceptions. For example, lymphocytes, although they divide slowly, are very sensitive to radiation (Coggle, 1983).

The table below presents the classification of tissues and organs by their degree of radiosensitivity.

Table 1. Classification of tissue radiosensitivity (based on Hall and Giaccia, 2006)

Radiosensitivity level	Tissue/Organ Type	Harmful dose (Gy)	Main effect
Very high (I)	Bone marrow, lymphoid tissue, gonads	0.5 – 2	Cell death, aplasia
High (II)	Intestinal epithelium, skin stratum corneum, eye lens	2 – 10	Desquamation, cataract
Middle (III)	Lungs, kidneys, liver, thyroid gland	10 – 20	Fibrosis, dysfunction
Low (IV)	Brain, spinal cord, bone, muscle	30 – 60	Necrosis (at high doses)
Very low (V)	Tendon, connective tissue	> 60	Structural changes

LD50 /30 is the dose that causes 50% mortality within 30 days of exposure . For humans, this figure is considered to be between 3.5–4.5 Gy, without medical care. Effective use of medical care can raise this limit to 6–7 Gy (Anno et al., 1989).

Acute radiation sickness (ARS) is divided into the following clinical syndromes depending on the dose .

syndromes of acute radiation sickness (based on Waselenko et al., 2004)

Syndrome	Dose (Gy)	Danger of death	Main characters	Start date
Subclinical	0.1 – 1	0%	Minimal symptoms	—
Hematopoietic	1 – 6	0–95%	Leukopenia, infection, bleeding	2–6 weeks
Gastrointestinal	6 – 10	>95%	Diarrhea, dehydration, sepsis	3–5 days
Cerebrovascular	>10	100%	Convulsions, coma, death	1–3 days

Radiogenic cancer is a prominent late effect of ionizing radiation. According to the International Commission on Radiation Protection (ICRP), a dose of 1 Sv increases the lifetime risk of developing cancer by approximately 5% (ICRP, 2007). The thyroid, lung, and mammary glands are the most sensitive organs for radiogenic cancer (NRC, 2006).

After irradiation, several degenerative changes are observed in cells: mitochondrial damage, endoplasmic reticulum disruption, and activation of apoptosis mechanisms. The role of the p53 protein is particularly important - it directs damaged cells to the apoptosis pathway (Lane, 1992).

Radiation fibrosis is a major degenerative process that develops late after radiation exposure and is characterized by collagen deposition due to overproduction of the cytokine TGF-beta (Martin et al., 2000). This process is clinically significant in the lungs (radiation pneumonitis), liver, and kidneys.

Damage to the vascular endothelium is central to the late effects of radiation. Radiation arteritis and capillary obliteration lead to prolonged tissue hypoxia, which in turn promotes secondary degeneration (Fajardo et al., 2001). Radiation osteonecrosis of bone, especially in the jaws (osteoradionecrosis), is a severe complication of radiation. It develops as a result of microvascular damage and osteoblast depletion (Marx and Tursun, 1985).

When studying the effects of ionizing radiation, it is necessary to pay attention first of all to the critical organelles that respond to the effects of radiation. In radiobiology, critical organs are those organs or tissues that are primarily damaged by ionizing radiation and that determine the general condition of the organism. Although radiation affects the entire body equally, some organs are at greater risk due to their biological function or sensitivity.

In radiobiology and radiation safety, critical organs are usually divided into the following groups :

Bone marrow. The bone marrow is the most radiosensitive organ in the body. Hematopoietic stem cells (CD34+ cells) are very sensitive to radiation, and their colony-forming ability is significantly reduced when exposed to 1–2 Gy (Dainiak et al., 2003). The critical dose to the bone marrow is 3–5 Gy. At this dose, severe aplastic anemia, granulocytopenia, and thrombocytopenia develop . Bone marrow transplantation has been shown to significantly increase the LD50 threshold (Thomas, 1999). Radiobiologically, the bone marrow D0 value (the dose that kills 63% of the cell population) is 1.3–1.5 Gy, which confirms its exceptionally high radiosensitivity (Hall and Giaccia, 2006).

Intestinal epithelium . The stem cell-rich epithelium of the small intestinal crypts is a rapidly renewing tissue (3–5 day renewal cycle) and is highly sensitive to radiation. At doses above 6 Gy, crypt aplasia and villous atrophy develop, leading to acute gastrointestinal syndrome (Potten, 1990). The gastrointestinal syndrome is clinically manifested by dehydration, electrolyte imbalance, bacterial translocation, and sepsis. The mortality rate from this syndrome exceeds 95% at doses of 6–10 Gy without medical intervention (Waselenko et al., 2004). The colonic epithelium is somewhat more radioresistant than the small intestine, but proctosigmoiditis and radiation colitis can develop at doses of 15–20 Gy (Hauer-Jensen et al., 2014).

Brain and central nervous system. Neurons in the adult brain are postmitotic and are considered radioresistant. However, the brain is not completely "radioresistant" in this sense - neuroglia, the blood-brain barrier and the microvasculature are sensitive to radiation (Tofilon and Fike, 2000). The clinical complications of brain radiation manifest themselves in two stages: acute encephalopathy (with doses above 3–4 Gy, edema and inflammation) and late complications - radiation necrosis and cognitive impairment (after 12–18 months, with doses above 60 Gy) (DeAngelis et al., 1989). In children, brain radiation is particularly dangerous - it has a long-term negative effect on cognitive development.

Gonads. The male gonads (testicles) are very sensitive to ionizing radiation. Spermatogonia have a $D_0 = 0.2-0.3$ Gy, making them among the most radiosensitive cells in the body . At doses of 1–4 Gy, transient azoospermia may develop, and at doses above 4 Gy, permanent sterility may develop (Centola et al., 1994).

The female gonads (ovaries) are relatively radioresistant, but early menopause develops at doses of 4–7 Gy. This effect is age- and radiation-dependent—younger women are more likely to recover fertility because they have more follicles to spare (Wallace et al., 1989). The genetic consequences of gonadal damage—gonadal mutations—are also of serious concern, although the UNSCEAR (2008) reports did not find a statistical increase in genetic disorders in Hiroshima and Nagasaki victims.

There are several mechanisms by which the body can biologically protect itself from radiation. DNA repair systems (NHEJ — Non-Homologous End Joining and HR — Homologous Recombination) serve to repair double-strand breaks. NHEJ is a fast but imprecise repair mechanism, while HR is more precise but slower (Khanna and Jackson, 2001).

The antioxidant system—the enzymes superoxide dismutase (SOD), catalase, and glutathione peroxidase— play an important role in neutralizing free radicals. A decrease in the activity of these enzymes after irradiation increases oxidative stress (Spitz et al., 2004).

Medical and technical protection . The basic principles of radiation protection are: time reduction, distance increase, and shielding (ICRP, 1990). Lead, concrete, and water are effective shielding materials for gamma radiation.

Radioprotectors—chemicals applied before radiation—reduce radiosensitivity. Amifostine (WR-2721) is the most commonly used radioprotector in clinical practice , scavenging free radicals through sulfhydryl groups (Yuhas, 1980). G-CSF (granulocyte colony-stimulating factor) and GM-CSF are effective in protecting the bone marrow from radiation and in restoring it after radiation. Filgrastim and pegfilgrastim have been shown to significantly increase the LD50 in BALB clinical trials (Dainiak et al., 2003).

Methods of gonadal protection . The following methods are used to protect the gonads from radiation in oncological patients: gonadal shielding (lead barriers), surgical removal of the gonads from the radiation field (oophorectomy), and pre-freezing of embryos and sperm (cryopreservation) (Lee et al., 2006).

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF KEY INDICATORS

Organ/Tissue	Critical dose (Gy)	D0 value (Gy)	Exposure time	Main complication
Bone marrow	3–5	1.3–1.5	2–6 weeks	Aplastic anemia, infection

Organ/Tissue	Critical dose (Gy)	D0 value (Gy)	Exposure time	Main complication
Small intestine	6–10	1.5–2.0	3–5 days	Gastrointestinal syndrome
Sperm/Spermatogonia	1–4	0.2–0.3	3–6 months	Azoospermia, sterility
Ovary	4–7	~2.0	Immediately–years	Early menopause
Brain (adult)	50–60	>5	Months–years	Necrosis, cognitive impairment
Brain (children)	18–24	~3	Months–years	Decreased IQ, stunted growth
Eye lens	2–10	~1	2–10 years	Cataract
Lungs	15–20	~3	1–6 months	Pneumonitis, fibrosis

Table 3. Comparative analysis of radiosensitivity indices of critical organs

The reviewed sources suggest several important conclusions regarding the biological effects of ionizing radiation. First, although the radiosensitivity of tissues is related to their mitotic activity, this relationship is complex, with exceptions such as lymphocytes. Second, the three main forms of acute radiation syndrome—hematopoietic, gastrointestinal, and cerebrovascular—are distinguished by clear dose thresholds, which is of practical importance for clinical prediction.

The most discussed issue in the literature is the cognitive consequences of brain irradiation. In recent years, studies by Monje et al. (2002) have shown that hippocampal neurogenesis is highly sensitive to irradiation, highlighting the need to reconsider the strategy of brain irradiation in oncological patients.

Modern reproductive medicine has made great strides in the field of gonadal protection — with the improvement of cryopreservation technologies, the chances of future childbearing for oncological patients have significantly increased. At the same time, several gaps have been identified in the literature : the possibilities of restoring brain regeneration mechanisms after radiation, the epigenetic mechanisms of low-dose radiation exposure, and the genetic factors determining individual radiosensitivity have not been fully studied.

Based on the above, the following conclusions were drawn:

The most sensitive organs in the human body to radiation are the bone marrow (blood-forming system) and the gonads . Even small doses of radiation (1–5 Gy) can completely stop their functioning or cause irreversible damage.

Because intestinal tissue regenerates very quickly, it responds rapidly to radiation. If the radiation dose reaches 6–10 Gy, it leads to intestinal dysfunction and a life-threatening gastrointestinal syndrome.

The brain of an adult is considered to be more resistant to radiation. However, the brain of a child and the area responsible for memory (hippocampus) in adults can be seriously damaged by radiation because new cells are constantly being formed there.

Effective technologies such as special chemicals (radioprotectants), freezing cells (cryopreservation), and physical barriers (shielding) are now being used to protect vital organs. Scientists are now focusing not only on large doses of radiation, but also on studying the effects of small

doses on heredity (epigenetics) and why some people are more sensitive to radiation than others at the genetic level.

This information is important in determining radiation treatment (radiotherapy) and radiation safety measures in medicine.

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